

Misleading meta-analysis on vitamin C for sepsis patients by Li (2018)

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Comment on:

Li J.

Evidence is stronger than you think: a meta-analysis of vitamin C use in patients with sepsis.

Crit Care. 2018 Oct 11;22(1):258.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30305111>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6180524>

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The Li study (1) is a meta-analysis which pooled the findings of a before–after study (2) with the findings of two small RCTs (3,4). This meta-analysis has several shortcomings which diminish the validity of the findings.

Firstly, the inclusion criteria were flawed. Observational studies may be biased due to confounding. Therefore, in evidence-based medicine, researchers almost always consider only randomised controlled trials, as is the case in the Cochrane Collaboration. Furthermore, in the Marik before-after study (2) vitamin C was not administered alone, but together with thiamine and hydrocortisone. Thus, even if the difference between the before and after periods was not confounded by changes in treatments, or by differences in the characteristics of patients, it is not possible to determine whether effects were caused by vitamin C or thiamine or hydrocortisone or by their combination. Thus, the Marik study is not a study on the effects of pure vitamin C and should not be pooled if the goal is to estimate the specific effects of vitamin C. Although Li (1) included a quality assessment of each included study (2-4), the methodological validity of the included studies was not taken into account.

In addition, the statistical analysis in the Li meta-analysis was not optimal. For binary outcomes, Li (1) calculated the pooled odds ratio (OR). However, the OR is appropriate for rare outcomes, but not for common outcomes. For common outcomes, the OR exaggerates the effects and should not be used (5-11).

For continuous outcomes, Li calculated the standardized mean difference (SMD), which uses one standard deviation (SD) as the unit of the scale. However, such a scale is difficult for medical

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

readers to interpret. For example, a recent survey concluded that “*Presenting results as a SMD ... was poorly understood and perceived as least useful*” (12). The Cochrane Collaboration discourages the use of SMD scale: “*the method assumes that the differences in SD among studies reflect differences in measurement scales and not real differences in variability among study populations. This assumption may be problematic in some circumstances where we expect real differences in variability between the participants in different studies... The overall intervention effect can also be difficult to interpret as it is reported in units of SD rather than in units of any of the measurement scales used in the review*” (13). It seems highly unlikely that the average reader can interpret whether the effect of 0.297 SD units on ICU length of stay is large or small (Fig. 1 in ref. 1). Pooling studies on the relative scale would have been much more informative since most medical readers are familiar with percentages (14,15).

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